

propionic acid (1 mole). After the addition was complete, the mixture was concentrated and cooled. Concentrated HCl was then added to precipitate the corresponding acid. It was then filtered, dried, and crystallised from acetone.

Piperazine 1,4-bis(Amino-dithiocarbamyl acetate/propionate):

In a 250 cc.r.b. flask fitted with a reflux condenser a mixture of amino-dithiocarbamyl-acetic/propionic acid (2 mole) and piperazine hexahydrate (1 mole) in ethanol, was refluxed on a steam bath for one hour. Subsequently the crude product, which was obtained on cooling, after the removal of the solvent, was triturated with petroleum ether and crystallised from acetone. The compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 1.

Pharmacology :

(a) *Toxicity test :* Firstly the compounds were tested for their toxicity i.e., the approximate LD 50 was determined.

For determination of approximate LD 50 (Lethal dose 50%) by dosage-mortality relationship, the procedure of Weil⁸ was followed.

Only eight compounds of this series were chosen for their toxicity and anti-Parkinsonian testing. The suspension of each compound was prepared in

Comp. No.	R	R'	% Protection of		Mortality after 24 hours	ALD ₅₀
			Salivation	Tremor		
1.	C ₂ H ₅ N	H	40	10	40	>1600
3.	C ₄ H ₉ NO	H	20	Nil	60	>1600
5.	C ₄ H ₉ N	H	60	Nil	60	>1000
11.	C ₆ H ₅ N	H	40	10	40	>1000
12.	<i>p</i> -C ₇ H ₇ N	H	20	Nil	20	>1600
15.	C ₆ H ₅ N	CH ₃	10	Nil	40	>1000
16.	<i>p</i> -C ₇ H ₇ N	CH ₃	Nil	10	20	>1500
18.	<i>m</i> -C ₇ H ₇ N	CH ₃	Nil	Nil	40	>1000

*Note : The compound Nos. of this table (table no. 2) are from the table no. 1).

gum-acasia and then injected in mice of either sex weighing 10-15 grams each intraperitoneally. For

TABLE 1

Compd. No.	R	R'	Yield	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	Analysis			
						% Nitrogen		% Sulphur	
						Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
1.	C ₂ H ₅ N	H	75	195	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	12.61	12.41	28.82	28.64
2.	C ₄ H ₁₀ N	H	80	205	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	11.20	11.15	26.50	25.15
3.	C ₄ H ₉ NO	H	80	215	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₆ S ₄	10.60	10.21	24.19	23.85
4.	C ₆ H ₁₀ N	H	75	210	C ₂₀ H ₃₆ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	10.68	10.15	24.42	24.62
5.	C ₄ H ₉ N	H	65	190	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	11.29	10.95	25.81	25.30
6.	C ₂ H ₅ N	CH ₃	70	198	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	11.86	11.25	27.11	26.54
7.	C ₄ H ₁₀ N	CH ₃	65	201	C ₂₀ H ₄₀ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	10.60	10.12	24.24	24.31
8.	C ₄ H ₉ NO	CH ₃	65	208	C ₂₀ H ₃₆ N ₄ O ₆ S ₄	10.07	9.84	23.02	22.58
9.	C ₃ H ₁₀ N	CH ₃	70	204	C ₂₂ H ₄₀ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	10.14	10.01	23.18	22.84
10.	C ₄ H ₉ N	CH ₃	72	195	C ₂₀ H ₃₆ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	10.68	10.22	22.51	22.11
11.	C ₆ H ₅ N	H	60	250	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	10.37	10.15	23.70	23.50
12.	<i>p</i> -C ₇ H ₇ N	H	65	245	C ₂₄ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	9.85	9.45	22.53	22.64
13.	<i>o</i> -C ₇ H ₇ N	H	55	248	C ₂₄ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	9.85	9.75	22.53	22.21
14.	<i>m</i> -C ₇ H ₇ N	H	54	241	C ₂₄ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	9.85	9.48	22.53	21.44
15.	C ₆ H ₅ N	CH ₃	60	205	C ₂₄ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	9.86	9.45	22.53	22.11
16.	<i>p</i> -C ₇ H ₇ N	CH ₃	65	195	C ₂₆ H ₃₆ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	9.39	9.41	21.47	21.24
17.	<i>o</i> -C ₇ H ₇ N	CH ₃	61	204	C ₂₆ H ₃₆ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	9.39	8.95	21.47	21.48
18.	<i>m</i> -C ₇ H ₇ N	CH ₃	63	202	C ₂₆ H ₃₆ N ₄ O ₄ S ₄	9.39	9.11	21.47	21.82

Note : All the compounds were recrystallised from acetone.

each compound five mice were taken for toxicity test. All the eight compounds possessed high ALD_{50} (> 1000 mg/kg) values which indicated there on toxicity of piperazine derivatives.

(b) *Anti-Parkinsonian activity*: This was determined at a dose of 200–400 mg/kg of each compound intraperitoneally against oxytremorine induced tremor and salivation in either sex of mice. The ALD_{50} values, mortality after 24 hours and percent protection of salivation and tremor is recorded in Table 2.

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